

Modularizing while Training: A New Paradigm for Modularizing DNN Models

Purpose

The purpose of the submitted artifact is to verify and validate the results in the paper [icse2024early-p197](#). This artifact aims to claim the "Available" and "Reusable" badges. We have prepared the trained models, resulting modules, and running logs for the experiments in the paper. The reproducible results include Tables 2 ~ 8.

This artifact provides three main functions, including *modular training*, *modularizing*, and *module reuse*. *Modular training* can train an N-class classification CNN model from scratch while optimizing its intra-module cohesion and inter-module coupling, resulting in a modular model. *Modularizing* can decompose the modular model into modules. Each module is responsible for one class and only retains the relevant convolutional kernels. *Module reuse* can reuse only the corresponding modules according to the classification of a target task rather than the entire model, thus reducing the inference cost.

Provenance

A docker image of the artifact is available at [Zenodo repository](#), which contains the source code files, trained models, resulting modules, and running logs. The source code files are also available at the [GitHub repository](#). The corresponding paper's preprint is available at [arXiv](#).

Setup

To use this artifact, you should have a server with the Docker environment. The server should have at least one GPU (NVIDIA Ampere A100 in our experiments). Then, download the [docker image](#) (i.e., `mwt.tar`) and execute it using the following commands:

```
> sudo docker load --input mwt.tar
> sudo docker run -it --name mwt --gpus all mwt:v1
```

After completing the installation, in the docker image, enter the directory using the following command:

```
> cd /workspace/MwT/src/examples
```

Usage

The docker image contains the trained models, resulting modules and running logs in `/workspace/MwT/data`. Also, we have prepared Python scripts in `/workspace/MwT/src/examples` for validating the major results in the paper including Tables 2 ~ 8.

NOTE: As the resulting modules from the paper were not entirely stored previously, we use the artifact to reproduce the experiments from scratch, including modular training, modularizing, and module reuse. Due

to the inherent randomness in training of deep learning models, the new results are not fully consistent with those presented in the paper. Nevertheless, the difference is slight, and some results obtained from the artifact are even better than those reported in the paper.

- Table 2: The comparison of standard training and the proposed MwT

Running the following command will get the results of Table 2 by summarizing the running logs in `/workspace/MwT/src/examples/table2`.

```
> python -u table2.py
```

If you want to modularize our trained modular model from scratch, please uncomment the codes in Lines 12 ~ 20 in `table2.py`. It will run `modularizer.py` to modularize a specified modular model.

The major parameters of `modularizer.py` include `--model`, `--dataset`, `--lr_model`, `--alpha`, `--beta`, `--batch_size`, and `--target_classes`, which represent the model architecture, the dataset used for modular training, the learning rate, the weighted factors for cohesion and coupling loss, the training batch size, and the class indices of modules intended for reuse, respectively.

- Table 3: The comparison of CNNSplitter and MwT

Running the following command will get the results of Table 3 by summarizing the running logs in `/workspace/MwT/src/examples/table3`.

```
> python -u table3.py
```

If you want to compute the results from scratch, please uncomment the codes in Lines 12 ~ 31. It will run `modularizer.py` to modularize a specified modular model.

- Table 4: The comparison of MwT and modularizing-after-training in time costs

Running the following command will perform modular training with 3 epochs, modularizing, and standard training with 3 epochs. You will see the time costs of each epoch required by modular training and standard training, respectively, and the time costs for modularizing.

```
> python -u table4.py
```

It will sequentially run `modular_trainer.py` and `modularizer.py` to perform modular training and modularizing to train and modularize a modular model. Additionally, it will execute `standard_trainer.py` to perform common training.

The major parameters of `modular_trainer.py` include `--model`, `--dataset`, `--lr_model`, `--alpha`, `--beta`, `--n_epochs`, which represent the model architecture, the dataset used for modular training, the learning rate, the weighted factors for cohesion and coupling loss, and the number of epochs for training, respectively.

- Table 5: The convolution kernel retention rate of MwT in reusing CNN modules

Running the following command will get the results of Table 5 by summarizing the running logs in `/workspace/MwT/src/examples/table5`.

```
> python -u table5.py
```

If you want to compute the results from scratch, please uncomment the codes in Lines 12 ~ 25. It will run `modularizer.py` to reuse the modules specified by the parameter `--target_classes` .

- Table 6: The computational costs of MwT in reusing CNN modules

Running the following command will get the results of Table 6 by summarizing the running logs in `/workspace/MwT/src/examples/table6` .

```
> python -u table6.py
```

If you want to compute the results from scratch, please uncomment the codes in Lines 12 ~ 19. It will run `cal_flops.py` to calculate the FLOPs required by different modules.

The major parameters of `cal_flops.py` include `--model` and `--dataset` , which represent the model architecture and the dataset used for modular training, respectively.

- Table 7: The test accuracy results of MwT in reusing CNN modules

Running the following command will get the results of Table 7 by summarizing the running logs that have been generated by `table5.py` .

```
> python -u table7.py
```

- Table 8: The comparison of MwT and CNNSplitter in reusing CNN modules in terms of KRR

Running the following command will get the results of Table 8 by summarizing the running logs in `/workspace/MwT/src/examples/table8` .

```
> python -u table8.py
```

If you want to compute the results from scratch, please uncomment the codes in Lines 12 ~ 35. It will run `exp_cnnsplitter_reusing/reuse_modules.py` and `modularizer.py` to reuse the modules generated by CNNSplitter and MwT.

- Train the modular model from scratch

If you want to train modular models from scratch, please run the following commands, which would take about 14 hours for 8 modular models.

```
> python -u train_modular_model_from_scratch.py
```

It will run `modular_trainer.py` to train a modular model from scratch.